

THE ROLE OF SCALE EFFECTS AND QFD IN INTEGRATED DESIGN FOR COMPOSITES

Vistasp M. Karbhari*, John M. Henshaw**, and Dick J. Wilkins*

*Center for Composite Materials, University of Delaware
Newark, Delaware 19716

**Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Tulsa
Tulsa, Oklahoma 74104

ABSTRACT

Motivation for the use of concurrent engineering in general and for composites in particular is developed. The concept of scale is briefly described and illustrated with examples of shape, microstructural, processing, and production volume scales. Scale is proposed as a way of relating traditional and difficult-to-relate aspects of design that must form the basis for an integrated engineering approach to composites. Quality Function Deployment (QFD) is briefly introduced and related to the authors' own concurrent engineering methodology, Total Quality Design (TQD). The five fundamental elements of TQD (definition, customers and customer wants, benchmarking, concepts, and go/no-go reviews) are introduced. Finally, the links between QFD and TQD are described in the areas of customer wants, benchmarking, and concepts.

Keywords: Scale Effects, QFD, Design Methodology

1. INTRODUCTION

During the last decade, American industry has faced increasing competition from abroad, and has even been described as being in a "product war" (1). The change to a global competitive economy has led to considerable soul searching with the attendant search for scapegoats ranging from trade regulations and practices to labor cost and short term strategy. Stimulated by this increased competition, newer technologies and changing markets, industries are responding to the competitive challenges by rethinking their approach to product development and manufacturing and are increasingly adopting Japanese methods of management and quality control. Strategic planning has assumed a position of great importance with choices determining key success factors, dictating

program continuation and shaping expectations for growth. Yet these plans, although based on the clearest strategic thinking and economic indicators, are thwarted by functional conflict. This is due to factors such as ill conceived programs and poor focus on product quality. Missed schedules, budget overruns, and the ultimate loss of market share are consequences of these factors. Product quality and customer satisfaction are rapidly becoming important competitive issues. It is essential for an industry to translate the voice of the customer into product features, thereby assuring that customer wants drive the product design and development (2,3,4).

It is against this background that we must view the potential of composites as replacements for traditional materials systems. Although composites are widely used in the aerospace and advanced technology areas, their full benefits are yet to be realized. Faced with increasing global competitiveness, the issues of high cost, product robustness, and the long lead times associated with product development are emerging in the forefront of challenges facing the American composites industry. It is unfortunate that developments in advanced materials technology and concurrent engineering seem to be along diverging paths, since the highly coupled nature of decisions necessary during composites product development are intimately connected with the rationale of concurrent engineering.

The tailorability of composites for specific applications has been one of its greatest attractions, and simultaneously one of its most perplexing challenges. The wide choice of materials combinations, processing methods, and shapes possible present bewildering selection problems. In the isotropic world of traditional materials it was possible to use tables, charts and simple formulae to check the validity of a concept, thereby relegating the need for specialists to the final stages before prototyping. This is not possible in composites, where specialists in different disciplines are needed almost routinely even at the stage of concept generation. Concurrent engineering thus is an ideal tool for composites product development, to the extent that were it not established in other fields, it would have been invented for composites out of necessity. The economics of the traditional iterative norm of product development make it necessary to promote an integrated approach. Other technologies have attempted to improve on the basic sequential product development approach. However, as has been noted previously (5), it is infrequently possible with composites to use a physically separable decision-making process during the selection of materials, processes and configuration. Every decision made during the product development process is intricately related to this set of three interacting decision areas. The concept of linking the attributes of performance, properties, microstructure and processing (Figure 1) has recently been discussed (6) as an extension to the notion of the necessity of recognizing design interactions. This allows for representation of customer wants through the attributes of performance required of the system/product.

2. SCALE ISSUES FOR COMPOSITES

The inherent scaling of constituents in a composite (Figure 2) suggests hierarchies encompassing the areas of mechanics, processing, and characterization, creating the need for the integration of knowledge of diverse fields towards the goal of a priori design of materials for an application, rather than the traditional approach of materials selection for an application. A composite can structurally be viewed in terms of a number of assemblages with the basic element being a set of concentric cylinders, with the matrix forming the outer sheath around the fiber. Scale control at this level would be needed to ensure that fibers are uniformly coated and thus are spaced uniformly apart during fabrication. At this level it is easy, for example, to specify microstructural control in terms of fiber spacing and scrim for boron and like fibers but next to impossible to do the same for carbon fibers. Laminae then are the building blocks for laminates, and herein the questions of laminae thickness and the formation of a matrix rich region between two adjacent laminae are of importance. Accurate control over the lamina dimensions as well as on the microstructural arrangement within, is dependent on the fiber scales. It is possible to specify fiber spacing and scrim for boron/epoxy tapes where the fibers were 4 mils in diameter, but this control is lost with graphite fibers. Due to the progression from boron to graphite as a reinforcement in laminated composites, the thick layer of resin between plies, as well as the repeatability of the thickness scale has been lost (7). The matrix rich region between laminae is affected by conditions during the manufacturing process and the thickness of this layer can be of great significance in the damage tolerance and resistance to failure of the material under service conditions. This is further complicated for hybrid composites, where alternate laminae may themselves have microstructures of different sizes. The use of laminates in panels then leads to the structural scale itself, with the attending problems of scaling for properties and choice of appropriate fabrication techniques. Of course these examples are all for the simplest of composite structures, and complexity of these scale issues is increased as the use of preforms or three dimensional reinforcement are considered.

The ability to design a material ultimately depends on the level of understanding of the mechanisms involved both at the microstructural level and at the level of process control. One way to represent the fundamental links in integrated engineering materials design is by a tetrahedron with each of the four vertices representing one of the controlling elements of materials design (Figure 1). The materials tetrahedron is an extension to the familiar structure-properties-performance model (8) and indeed this model has been suggested in very similar form by Cohen (9). The links between the vertices can be thought of in terms of vectors, indicative of the direction and extent of control of one aspect over another. As an example we consider the relationships and influence of processing on the three other vertices - microstructure, properties and performance. Processing paths and parameters influence performance attributes as a single directed vector array. However there is a give and take relationship between processing and microstructure, wherein the former can

dictate the resultant microstructure, but in turn may have to be changed in order to achieve a required microstructure. Such a dualism is inherent in processes such as injection molding.

There is sometimes confusion in differentiating two elements of the materials tetrahedron: properties and performance. Properties are general measures or fundamental measurable characteristics of a material system, while performance is case-specific and subjective, describing the behavior of a structure or component during service or during its fabrication. Properties only indicate performance, they do not define it. Performance is what the customer wants. Properties are how engineers measure what the customer wants. Whereas there exist two way links between properties and the other two vertices of the tetrahedron - processing and microstructure, that between performance and the same two vertices is a one way link. Processing affects performance, microstructure lays limits on it and properties are metrics that indicate it. The differentiation becomes clearer when the QFD model is considered (as in Section 3). Performance is the "what" of QFD, whereas properties are the "how".

In the remainder of this section, we will briefly review some examples of scales for composites. A more complete review may be found in (6).

2.1 Shape Scales Geometric shape cuts across all four corners of the materials tetrahedron. It can be argued that "shape" in itself is just as fundamental as the four vertices of the materials tetrahedron; however, in the context of this paper it is viewed as a set of difficult-to-define metrics that play important roles in translating the voice of the customer into a product.

Shapes are most often scaled with simple heuristics (flat plate, curved plate, surface of revolution, etc.), although it is apparent that the requirement of shape is a discriminator of processing alternatives (10). The describing functions and metrics are an important topic of ongoing research (11, 12). With the development of suitable metrics shape scales could serve as important links in the optimization of component design based on both form and function (or performance).

2.2 Microstructural Scales At least two scales for the microstructure of composites exist that can be defined relatively simply: a fiber length scale, and a fiber volume fraction scale. However, these two scales only partially describe composite microstructure. In addition, they do not serve as very good links to the other elements in the materials tetrahedron. Other scales are needed to describe and evaluate microstructure-related elements such as microstructural flexibility, part-to-part microstructural repeatability and the multi-dimensionality of microstructure. Microstructural scales such as flexibility and repeatability are much more difficult to quantify, but are no less significant for this difficulty, being of immense importance in production economics.

2.3 Links to Materials Processing The link between microstructure and processing may be the most important of the links depicted in the materials tetrahedron. The microstructure-processing link through the concept of scale embodies the understanding of how small changes in both will influence the properties of the material and the performance components fabricated from it. The choice of processing path can be shown to influence the selection of size of reinforcement, again emphasizing the importance of the scale concept in composites design integration. This link between processing method and microstructure is a useful discriminator in concept "deselection" (the process of eliminating the "bad" choices) as it is a source of many of the attributes of quality and repeatability. The chosen processing method determines not only the possible range of fiber orientations, but also the ranges of fiber volume fractions and lengths, thus influencing load carrying capacity.

2.4 Production Volume Scale Scale in the context of production volume is significant for composites. The influence of production scale (number of parts to be fabricated per unit time or in total) on structure/microstructure scales is linked to process economics: for small-scale production, certain processes are feasible. For intermediate and large scales, other processes come into play. Unlike many of the scale relationships introduced above, the relationships here are almost entirely heuristic, and are thus subject to rapid and unpredictable change. We schematically depict an example of these heuristics for the trade-offs involved in the selection of a process based on both production volume necessary and the requirements of part size in Figure 3. It is obvious that although designers have often thought of processes as being interchangeable, there is limited overlap in the regimes of applicability of the different processes. Production volume thus serves as a useful scale of discrimination. An important aim of composites process developers is to expand the upper and lower bounds (on various scales, but in this case specifically the production volume scale) throughout which designers will consider their particular process.

2.5 Geometric Size Scale Scale in the context of the geometric envelope of a component, or of the structure, (the size scale) has a similar relationship to composites as the production scale. This time, however, the link is provided by the physical capacities of the production processes themselves. Certain processes are capable of producing parts only in a restricted size range. To raise the upper bound on the geometric scale (typically the more important bound) process developers may reduce temperature or pressure requirements or reduce fixed costs by improving on the efficiency of the process or using cheaper, or more reliable materials with less scrap and wastage. To bring down the lower bound would require improvements in the precision of processing or tooling equipment or a reduction in the applicable microstructural scale of the raw or intermediate material forms.

3. QFD AND COMPOSITES

In this section we briefly introduce Quality Function Deployment (QFD) (4) and relate it to our own concurrent engineering methodology, Total Quality Design (TQD) (13).

The QFD process may be introduced graphically, as shown in Figure 4. The essence of QFD is the transformation from a qualified set of objects (the "what" in Figure 4) to a quantified set (the "how" in Figure 4). The relationships among the whats and hows, and the qualitative and quantitative information are all scaling issues.

The basic model described in our earlier paper (6), that of linking the corners of the materials tetrahedron through various scales, may be looked at in terms of the elements in an integrated methodology, within the tenets of QFD, but specific to the early design decisions that are so critical to composites. The materials tetrahedron and the various scales described in Section 2 then become tools in the decision process, with one or more of the "scales" serving as indicators of acceptance or rejection at each review stage. The idea of linking scale and QFD is expanded upon in Section 4.

QFD forms a rough subset of the TQD methodology. We will introduce the five elements of this process and highlight the advantages we have observed through their use in composites-related projects. For those familiar with Total Quality Management (TQM) techniques, it should be apparent that TQD serves to enhance and emphasize the design and manufacturing elements within such a methodology.

3.1 Definition

3.1.1 **The Team** The formation of an integrated product development team is perhaps the most critical aspect of any successful project. The core of this team is the facilitator, the customer, and the specialists (or generalists). We stress that the actual number of members in a team is dependent on the scope and specific requirements of the project. It is, however, essential that it be multi-faceted and multi-functional, with the members capable of communicating their relevant expertise towards a common goal. It is in this aspect that emphasis on the human aspects of concurrent engineering related to training, motivation and facilitation are required.

3.1.2 **The Mission** The strategic choices made by management in response to the customer requirements in terms of goals and schedules give meaning and direction to the various activities necessary for a successful product. The mission serves to guide implementation, but should be wide enough so as to permit adaptation and change during development as well as not anticipating a specific method of solution. Key to the mission are the criteria of schedule and cost, which together define the scope of a project or

program. An effective project team is essential in determining tradeoffs between schedules and costs associated with the mission.

3.2 Customers and Customer Wants

3.2.1 Customers The primary customer must serve as a focal point for the entire development process, and should be part of the team, with the objective of having the team continuously driven to be responsive to market requirements and the satisfaction of this member. Quality is defined by the customer. In the industrial world there are often multiple customers ranging from the user of the end product to a share-holder.

3.2.2 Customer Wants Under the new paradigm, customer wants are the primary driving forces of product development. Care should be taken to determine these wants, some of which may be intangibles (such as aesthetics), and define them in terms of technical requirements and specifications. Quality perception in terms of expectations and satisfaction need to be carefully considered after benchmarking. With composites, it may be possible to satisfy wants through modifications in materials, manufacturing methods, or configuration, or a combination of these. Composites design and manufacture can be thought of as means of creating possibilities associated with specific customer wants.

3.3 Benchmarking

3.3.1 Competitive Benchmarking It is necessary to compare the attributes of competing products. This can result in the adoption of existing concepts or in improving the available product attributes. In composites, care should be taken when benchmarking products made using different processing routes and materials as the metrics of comparison may not be the same, unlike in benchmarking of products made of traditional materials. There may be instances where instead of attributes, organizations themselves or aspects of marketing, services rendered, or product development techniques used by leaders in industry are used as benchmarks. Clear examples of this are the standards set by L.L. Bean for the mail order business, American Express in the credit card industry, and IBM in the computer industry, which are pursued by others as shining examples of "How to satisfy and keep customers."

3.3.2 Quality Metrics These are measuring sticks used to compare quantities corresponding to customer wants. They are quantifiable and/or tangible attributes on the basis of which comparisons can be made and concepts differentiated. Quality metrics can be thought of as descriptors of technical requirements which correlate to customer wants and through which these wants can be satisfied.

3.4 Concepts

3.4.1 Concept Generation It is essential that at the outset many concepts, some new and others adaptations of existing products or features, be generated. Creativity and innovation are the keys here. Although this stage is generally considered to be the focal point for creativity, it is stressed that for the best use of composites, creativity and innovation must be an integral part of the entire product development process, not just at the concept generation phase.

3.4.2 Concept Selection The large number of concepts generated through the TQD process has to be whittled down to the best one or two. This is made necessary to optimize the use of resources in further developing and scrutinizing the best concepts. The most important quality metrics are used as criteria for deselection of concepts.

3.5 Go/No-Go Reviews At the end of concept selection, management and the team have to decide whether it is worthwhile to further develop a concept. The TQD process recognizes that product innovation and development is a process that needs to be managed. The Go/No-Go reviews serve as gates at which assessments are made. Each review is a critical decision point in the product development process. If the decision is a "Go" both management and the team have determined with a high degree of confidence that further development expenditures are justifiable. If the decision is a "No-Go", management and the team have identified the technology gaps, economic issues, and competition conditions that make further development imprudent.

4. LINKING QFD, TOD AND SCALE

Which elements of TQD serve as links between scale and design? How does scale interact with TQD at each stage?

QFD is used to translate customer wants into technical requirements at each stage of the product development process. Both QFD and TQD draw their strength from their ability to serve as efficient planning tools and help in keeping events in perspective and along the right path as the design process proceeds from conceptualization through production.

4.1 Links to Customer Wants, and Benchmarking The major technical impediment to the direct use of QFD stems from the coupling between attributes related to design requirements and manufacturing operations. In terms of the TQD process described earlier these are linked to customer wants, quality metrics, and benchmarking. The coupling is exposed through the proper identification of metrics, which can be thought of as scales of comparison, as described in Section 2. The use of scales in terms of comparative estimates among design, manufacturing, and production such as production volume and geometric size or microstructural control serve in an upstream quality product design- oriented activity

rather than a two-step engineering design and manufacturing-oriented form of production. Such a process addresses three broad problems faced by American industry: disregard for the voice of the customer, lack of comparative information necessary for product and process design in the early stages of decision-making, and differing interpretation of requirements and specifications by the different disciplines involved in the development of a composites product. The use of scales of comparison make it possible to set priorities for product and manufacturing related characteristics, as well as highlight areas of overlap between competing materials and/or processes. The scales of comparison serve not only as discriminators but also as a means of identifying interactions that are necessary for efficient product-process integration. The identification of such interaction and tradeoffs is important, more so because unless approached in accord with the composites paradigm instead of the corresponding metals one, they are difficult for designers to comprehend early in the design process.

4.2 Links to Concept Generation and Selection

Scales such as production volume serve as both customer wants and quality metrics. The specification of a desirable range of production volume by the customer almost immediately drives the process into the concurrent activities of benchmarking and concept generation and selection. Other scales such as microstructural control, which can be regarded as a set of quality metrics, also serve as a catalyst for concept generation with regard to manufacturing processes such a liquid molding within which a variety of microstructures is possible.

5. CONCLUSION

The concept of scale does not constitute an integrated design methodology. It is merely a way of relating the many difficult-to-relate aspects of design. In that sense, scale is related to design methodology, as represented by QFD and TQD, which may be thought of as transformation processes linked together by scale. If we look at concurrent engineering through the QFD metaphor, then TQD and QFD itself (among other methodologies) become the "what". The specific scales of composites design, both well and poorly understood and quantified, become the "how".

REFERENCES

1. R.G. Cooper, Business Horizons, May-June 1990, p. 44-54.
2. D. Clausing and B.H. Simpson, Quality Progress, January 1990, p.41-44.
3. A.A. Kenny, Quality Progress, June 1988, p. 30-32
4. L.P. Sullivan, Quality Progress, June 1986.
5. J.M. Henshaw, A Framework and Tools for the Early Decisions in the Product Development Process, Ph.D. dissertation, University of Delaware, 1989.

6. V.M. Karbhari, J.M. Henshaw, and D.J. Wilkins, SAMPE International Symposium, **36**, (1991).
7. C. Rogers, "The Influence of Design Concepts and Manufacturing Methods on Life", presented at the Center for Composite Materials, University of Delaware, April 7, 1989
8. L.H. Van Vlack, Elements of Materials Science and Engineering, Addison-Wesley, New York, 1986, pp. 10-12.
9. M. Cohen, in forward to ref. 4, p.xx.
10. D.J. Wilkins, "Design for Manufacturing", plenary lecture, 1990 University-Industry Symposium, University of Delaware, September 1990.
11. J.J. Shah and A.S. Bhatnagar, Manufacturing Review, **2** (3), 204 (1989).
12. A. Bhadra and G.W. Fischer, Manufacturing Review, **1** (1), 44 (1988).
13. J.M. Henshaw, D.J. Wilkins, and V.M. Karbhari, "The Total Quality Design Workbook", Center for Composite Materials, Report 90-29, University of Delaware.

BIOGRAPHIES

VISTASP M. KARBHARI is a visiting scientist at the Center for Composite Materials at the University of Delaware. He completed his Ph.D. on scale effects in design and fracture of composites under the advisorship of Dr. D.J. Wilkins in 1990. His research interests include design methodology, mechanics of composites, fracture mechanics and composites manufacturing science.

JOHN M. HENSHAW is an Assistant Professor of Mechanical Engineering at the University of Tulsa. He received a Ph.D. in Materials Science at the University of Delaware in 1989. He is a registered Professional Engineer having spent 7 years in the energy industries prior to his doctoral studies. His research interests include materials science, design methodology, composites manufacturing, and environmental issues related to materials.

DICK J. WILKINS is President of the newly formed Delaware Technology Park and Professor of Mechanical Engineering at the University of Delaware. From 1986 to 1990, he was Director of the Center for Composite Materials at the University of Delaware. His research interests include design integration, creativity, composites manufacturing science, durability and damage tolerance, and structural mechanics. He previously spent 17 years with the Fort Worth Division of General Dynamics, where he was responsible for numerous structures technology development activities in composites, including the U.S. Air Force structural certification of the first production graphite-epoxy structures, the empennage of the F-16 aircraft. Dr. Wilkins earned B.S., M.S., and Ph.D. degrees at the University of Oklahoma. He is the current President of the American Society for Composites (ASC).

FIGURE 1 The Materials Tetrahedron

FIGURE 2 Inherent scaling in a composite

FIGURE 3. Example of comparison of production and size scales.

FIGURE 4 The QFD process